

The Role of Motivation on Institutional Development: Selecting the Appropriate Theory for Milton Margai College of Education and Technology

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Abstract:

An administrator's duties in today's corporate world are diversified. Not only do managers need to be versed in finance, economics, and information systems; it is now essential for them to have a firm grasp on organizational behavior and psychology. They must know how their employees think and what makes them think that way. Meeting the demands of this work prompted the researchers to seek secondary data to be able to bring to light the concept of motivation. It also led the researchers into looking for appropriate materials on the type of motivation. The research gives us a faster glimpse on the types of motivation (Intrinsic rewards are those which are felt directly, and include accomplishment, increased self-esteem, and new skills; extrinsic rewards are provided by an outside agent and include bonuses, praise, and promotions). The theories were also looked into, and their relevance brought out as to how they will help the institution. At the end of this research work, it is believed to help develop the institution by improving on employees' performance for the achievement of the institution's goal.

Keywords: Motivation, theories, goal-setting, Milton Margai, implication.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

All organizations are concerned with what should be done to achieve sustained high levels of performance through people. This means giving close attention to how individuals can best be motivated through such means as incentives, rewards, leadership and, importantly, the work they do and the organizational context within which they carry out that work. The aim is to develop motivation processes and a work environment that will help to ensure that individuals deliver results in accordance with the expectations of management. Motivation theory examines the process of motivation. It explains why people at work behave in the way they do in terms of their efforts and the directions they are taking. It describes what organizations can do to encourage people to apply their efforts and abilities in ways that will further the achievement of the organization's goals as well as satisfy their own needs. It is also concerned with job satisfaction – the factors that create it and its impact on performance. In understanding and applying motivation theory, the aim is to obtain added value through people in the sense that the value of their output exceeds the cost of generating it.

Unfortunately, approaches to motivation are too often underpinned by simplistic assumptions about how it works. The process of motivation is much more complex than many people believe. People have different needs, establish different goals to satisfy those needs and take different actions to achieve those goals. It is wrong to assume that one approach to motivation fits all. That is why the assumptions underlying belief in the virtues of performance-related pay as a means of providing a motivational incentive are simplistic. Motivational practices are most likely to function effectively if they are based on proper understanding of what is involved. Further below we will look into the concept of motivation and what really it entails.

The Milton Margai Teachers College was established in 1963, and it was first housed at Tower Hill in Freetown. The primary focus for the establishment of such an institution was to train teachers for the lower tier of secondary school ranging from form one through form three.

Before 1967, teachers who graduated from this institution were awarded either with a Teacher's Certificate, or a Teacher's Advanced Certificate (TAC). In 1967 a new three-year programme was introduced, the curriculum was restructured, and both the TC and TAC phased out and was replaced with the Higher Teachers Certificate (HTC).

A new system of education was introduced in the country by the then military government, In 1995, in response to the needs of the new 6-3-3-4 system of education, a Bachelor of Education degree programme was introduced in 2002. Milton Margai merged with Freetown Technical Institute and the Hotel and Tourism Training Institute at Brookfield. This latest restructuring transforms the college into a Polytechnic.

1.1 Research Aim

The development and success of any educational institution are dependent on the motivation theory it uses. As institutions are competing on retaining their best staffs, the use of appropriate motivation theory is of great importance. Staff retention does not only mean providing them with financial rewards like incentives, salary bonuses, etc.; rather consideration should always be given to rewards like recognition, staff development, etc. The focus of this study is to assess the various theories of motivation and recommend a suitable one for Milton Margai College of Education and Technology.

1.2 Research Objectives

The study is focused on bringing out the different motivation theories as for how they are being addressed by different scholars and school of thoughts. A variety of secondary data will be used as the objectives are highlighted. The general objectives are outlined as follows:

- Defining the concept of motivation as seen by various scholars.
- Describe intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and its relevance in developing Milton Margai College.
- Explain the theories of motivation(Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, Douglas McGregor theory X, and theory Y, etc.)
- Establishing the implications of these theories

1.3 Significance of the study

The significance of motivation is apparent, which makes it more useful for the appropriate theory to be used within this educational sector. For us to be able to achieve our goal we need motivation. Motivation stands as one of the paramount factors that determine us reaching our goals. Having said that, one will begin to imagine what progress we will make if we make motivation as a centerpiece in our administrative duties.

Positive emotions do not always represent motivation as fear of achieving a goal can also serve as a real motivating factor. A simple example of negative motivation is that of stress as most people might have the tendency of becoming narrow-sighted when they are stressed. Some school of thought will argue that achieving a goal motivates people; this might not be true. What really motivates workers are the rewards for reaching the goals of the satisfaction they get for being important. It is because of this perception that we have of motivation that prompted this work so that Milton Margai College of Education and Technology will adopt the best motivation theory to achieve its desired goals.

2.0 Literature Review

High performance is achieved by well-motivated people who are prepared to exercise discretionary effort. Even in fairly basic roles, Hunter *et al.* (1990) found that the difference in value added discretionary performance between 'superior' and 'standard' performers was 19 percent. For highly complex jobs it was 48 percent. To motivate people, it is necessary to appreciate how motivation works. This means understanding motivation theory and how the theory can be put into practice. Motivation is the answer to the question "**Why we do what we do?**" The motivation theories try to figure out what the "**M**" is in the equation: "**M motivates P**" (Motivator motivates the Person). It is one of most important duty of an entrepreneur to motivate people. (We strongly believe that motivating people with visionary and shared goals is more favorable than motivating through tactics, incentives or manipulation or through simple carrot and stick approaches because motivating with vision is natural whereas the former is artificial and ephemeral).

Motivating other people is about getting them to move in the direction you want them to go in order to achieve a result. Motivating yourself is about setting the direction independently and then taking a course of action that will ensure that you get there. Motivation can be described as goal-directed behavior. People are motivated when they expect that a course of action is likely to lead to the attainment of a goal and a valued reward – one that satisfies their needs and wants.

Well-motivated people engage in discretionary behavior – in the majority of roles, there is scope for individuals to decide how much effort to exert. Such people may be self-motivated, and as long as this means they are going in the right direction to attain what they are there to achieve, then this is the best form of motivation. Most of us, however, need to be motivated to a greater or lesser degree.

2.1 CONCEPT OF MOTIVATION

A precise definition of motivation is elusive since the concept involves numerous characteristics and perceptions of the employee and the current situation. But it is characterized by a certain level of willingness on the part of the employee to increase effort, to the extent that this exertion also satisfies some need or desire. At a basic level, it can be seen that motivation is about 'motives' and 'needs.' Motives are the internal drives and energies of an employee; they direct behavior, which results in outcomes. There are a number of competing definitions, so identifying the one that is just right in relation to reward management is practically impossible. It is better therefore to consider the common underlying assumptions which suggest that motivation is:

- an individual phenomenon – people are unique, and this means that motivation theories usually allow for uniqueness to be reflected in behavior;
- intentional and results in behaviors that are the result of conscious choices;
- a multifaceted concept, which involves (a) factors that arouse people to action (b) choice of behavior and (c) choices about the persistence and intensity of behavior;
- valid as a theory because it helps predict behavior by explaining what prompts the behavior of people, which means that it has very little concern with simply describing or categorizing behavior.

A motive is a reason for doing something. Motivation is concerned with the factors that influence people to behave in certain ways. The three components of motivation as listed by Arnold et al. (1991) are:

- **direction** – what a person is trying to do;
- **effort** – how hard a person is trying;
- **persistence** – how long a person keeps on trying?

Going through the algorithms of the concept, it suggests that motivation is initiated by the conscious or unconscious recognition of unsatisfied needs. These needs create wants, which are desires to achieve or obtain something. Goals are then established which it is believed will satisfy these needs and wants and a behavior pathway is selected which it is expected will achieve the goal. If the goal is achieved, the need will be satisfied, and the behavior is likely to be repeated the next time a similar need emerges. If the goal is not achieved, the same action is less likely to be repeated.

2.2 TYPES OF MOTIVATION

Motivation at work can take place in two ways. First, people can motivate themselves by seeking, finding and carrying out work (or being given work) that satisfies their needs or at least lead them to expect that their goals will be achieved. Secondly, people can be motivated by management through such methods as pay, promotion, praise, etc.

There are two types of motivation as originally identified by Herzberg et al. (1957):

2.2.1 Intrinsic motivation comes from within the inner self of an individual or we can say that these are the internal factors that are driven by the interest and enjoyment in the job itself what the individual is doing rather than relying on the external factors. The intrinsic motivation can be produced within then individuals by identifying their psychological needs related to the jobs they are performing. Involving the employees in the

decision making process by letting them participate in giving suggestions regarding designation of jobs, their interest in the related jobs, their priority related to the specific job, comfortable level to a certain job, etc.; this practice can help managers to increase the intrinsic motivation of the employees of the organization and to increase the efficiency and effectiveness by achieving goals within specified time.

2.2.2 Extrinsic motivation All the external factors like rewards such as money, promotions, recognition, coercion, threats of punishments are responsible for the extrinsic motivation for the individual. Likewise, competition is one most commonly used extrinsic factor that encourages the performer to win and beat others. A crowd cheering on the individual and trophies are also extrinsic factors to make the individual win the game.

2.3 THEORIES OF MOTIVATION

Motivation theories can be classified broadly into two different perspectives: Content and Process theories. Content Theories deal with “what” motivates people, and it is concerned with individual needs and goals. Maslow, Alderfer, Herzberg, and McClelland studied motivation from a “content” perspective. Process Theories deal with the “process” of motivation and is concerned with “how” motivation occurs. Vroom, Porter & Lawler, Adams, and Locke studied motivation from a “process” perspective.

2.3.1 CONTENT THEORY

A content theory of motivation is concerned with the internal factors that actuate human behavior. Four of the most common content theories are.

- Maslow's hierarchy of needs
- Alderfer's ERG theory
- Herzberg's motivator-hygiene theory (Herzberg's dual factors theory)
- McClelland's learned needs or three-needs theory are some of the major content theories

2.3.1.1 NEEDS

i. Maslow

When motivation theory is being considered the first theory what is being recalled is Maslow's hierarchy of needs which he introduced in his 1943 article named “A Theory of Human Motivation.” According to this theory, individual strives to seek a higher need when lower needs are fulfilled. Once a lower-level need is satisfied, it no longer serves as a source of motivation. Needs are motivators only when they are unsatisfied.

- In the first level, **physiological needs** exist which include the most basic needs for humans to survive, such as air, water, and food.
- In the second level, **safety needs** exist which include personal security, health; well-being and safety against accidents remain.
- In the third level, **belonging needs** exist. This is where people need to feel a sense of belonging and acceptance. It is about relationships, families, and friendship. Organizations fulfill this need for people.
- In the fourth level, **self-esteem needs** remain. This is where people look to be respected and to have self-respect. Achievement needs, respect for others are at this level.
- In the top-level, **self-actualization needs** exist. This level of need pertains to realizing the person's full potential.

ii. David McClelland (need for achievement)

He proposed a context for understanding needs in people, which holds significance in understanding motivations and behaviors. It is subdivided into three categories: the Need for Achievement, the Need for Affiliation, and the Need for Power.

The **Need for Achievement** refers to the notion of getting ahead and succeeding. The Need for Affiliation is the desire to be around people and be well received socially. It also includes the desire for being a member of a group and conformity. The Need for Power is the desire for control over others and over you. It confers the need to be able to exercise direction in the world surrounding you and cause things to happen. Individuals who have

high needs for achievement tend to engage in competitive activities in order to fulfill this desire. Individuals who need to feel affiliated will tend to join clubs, groups, and teams to satiate that want. Individuals who have the need for power will seek activities which likewise satisfy this need, such as, to run for high positions in organizations and to seek out opportunities to exercise that dominance.

This is not to say that one person cannot have needs spanning all three categories. A person may have the need for affiliation at the same time they have the need for power. While this may initially seem contradictory, there are instances where both needs can be fulfilled. Also, timing may connote different strengths of needs at different moments. So, while a person may strongly feel the need to affiliate during times of loneliness, they may at another time feel the strong need for power when instructed to organize an event. Needs may arise and be changed out of a change of context.

2.3.1.2 ERG MODEL (Alderfer's)

Clayton Alderfer developed a revised version of Maslow's hierarchy on needs in 1969. The ERG theory looks at the Existence, Relatedness, and Growth needs as a less rigid hierarchy. It addresses some of the limitations of Maslow's theory. There are similarities and differences from Maslow. Similarities include reducing Maslow to three needs since some overlap. Thus ERG's are the three. The differences include allowing different levels of needs to be pursued simultaneously. Also, it allows for the order to be different for different people. The theory acknowledges that if higher levels remain unfulfilled, there may be a regression to lower level needs in what is known as a frustration-regression principle.

Alderfer's theory is useful and demonstrates some important findings of how we as individuals move up and down the levels of the model and seek satisfaction of needs. The model shows how different levels are all operative at the same time and a frustration dimension can be in operation forcing us to seek more satisfaction of goals and needs at a lower level when blocked at a higher level. This is often called the frustration-regression element.

Motivation and performance in the workplace are strongly tied together. As a Leader, it is important to understand motivational theories and how these help you understand your own and others behavior and performance outcomes at work. The model suggests that motivation is very personal and complex and always moving. It also shows that a 'one size fits all' approach to motivating employees will be less than optimum due to the individual and changing levels and needs an individual will constantly be experiencing.

2.3.1.3. TWO- FACTOR MODEL (Fredrick Herzberg)

In the 1950 and 1960's Fredrick Herzberg examined employee satisfaction. His research was aimed at how attitude affected Motivation. To do this, he wanted to know in what situations people felt. Herzberg's theory is called the Motivation-Hygiene Theory and has Motivators-Hygiene Factors. It is sometimes called the Two-Factor Theory. He believes that two groups of factors affect motivation at work. Intrinsic 'motivators' (relate to Maslow's higher needs) such as achievement and recognition can positively influence motivation, while extrinsic 'hygiene factors' (relate to Maslow's lower needs) such as pay and working conditions can negatively impact motivation if they are not satisfactory. Hygiene factors do not motivate, but can negatively affect motivation if they are absent. Motivators improve motivation but do not eliminate dissatisfaction.

Although Herzberg is most noted for his famous 'hygiene' and motivational factors theory, he was essentially concerned with people's well-being at work. Underpinning his theories and academic teachings, he was basically attempting to bring more humanity and caring into the workplace. He and others like him did not develop their theories to be used as 'motivational tools' purely to improve organizational performance. They sought instead primarily to explain how to manage people properly, for the good of all people at work.

Herzberg's research proved that people would strive to achieve 'hygiene' needs because they are unhappy without them, but once satisfied the effect soon wears off - satisfaction is temporary. Then as now, poorly managed organizations fail to understand that people are not 'motivated' by addressing 'hygiene' needs. People

are only truly motivated by enabling them to reach for and satisfy the factors that Herzberg identified as real motivators, such as achievement, advancement, development, etc., which represent a far deeper level of meaning and fulfillment.

Examples of Herzberg's 'hygiene' needs (or maintenance factors) in the workplace are Policy, relationship with supervisor, work conditions, salary, company car, status, security, relationship with subordinates, personal life. Herzberg's research identified that true motivators were other completely different factors, notably: Achievement, recognition, work itself, responsibility and advancement.

2.3.1.4. THEORY X AND THEORY Y (McGregor)

McGregor, an American social psychologist, proposed his famous X-Y theory in his 1960 book 'The Human Side of Enterprise.' Theory x and theory y are still referred to commonly in the field of management and motivation, and whilst more recent studies have questioned the rigidity of the model, Mcgregor's X-Y Theory remains a valid basic principle from which to develop positive management style and techniques. McGregor's XY Theory remains central to organizational development, and to improving organizational culture. McGregor's X-Y theory is a salutary and simple reminder of the natural rules for managing people, which under the pressure of day-to-day business are all too easily forgotten. McGregor maintained that there are two fundamental approaches to managing people. Many managers tend towards theory x and generally get poor results. Enlightened managers use theory y, which produces better performance and results, and allows people to grow and develop.

Theory x ('Authoritarian Management' Style)

The average person dislikes work and will avoid it if he/she can. Therefore most people must be forced with the threat of punishment to work towards organizational objectives. The average person prefers to be directed; to avoid responsibility; is relatively unambitious, and wants security above all else.

Theory y ('Participative Management' Style)

The effort in work is as natural as work and play. People will apply self-control and self-direction in the pursuit of organizational objectives, without external control or the threat of punishment. Commitment to objectives is a function of rewards associated with their achievement. People usually accept and often seek responsibility. The capacity to use a high degree of imagination, ingenuity, and creativity in solving organizational problems is wide, not narrowly, distributed in the population. In industry, the intellectual potential of the average person is only partly utilized.

2.3.2 PROCESS/COGNITIVE THEORY

The group of motivational theories that fall under the umbrella category of Process Theories of Motivation is based on the use of our rational thought processes or cognitive processing abilities. Unlike a drive or needs-based theory, the process theories of motivation explore a step above the biological levels to examine how we think and rationalize our actions. Processor cognitive theory can certainly be more useful to managers than needs theory because it provides more realistic guidance on motivation techniques. The processes are:

- expectations (**expectancy theory**);
- goal achievement (**goal theory**);
- feelings about equity (**equity theory**).

2.3.2.1 Expectancy Theory (Vroom, Porter, and Lawler)

The Expectancy Theory of motivation suggests that human beings are driven to accomplish a goal when they deem the benefits of achieving the goal desirable and because it seems likely that the goal can be reached. If a

goal fits into the framework of an individual's expectations, appearing worthwhile and doable, he will be motivated to reach it. Three factors are implicated in the process of motivation for the Expectancy Theory. The goal must have a valence (or value.) A sense of instrumentality, or belief that there is a way to complete the goal must be present. Finally, the individual must have a sense of expectancy, meaning that he feels capable of taking steps to achieve the goal. Thus, the expectancy theory concentrates on the following three relationships:

- Effort-performance relationship: What is the likelihood that the individual's effort is recognized in his performance appraisal?
- Performance-reward relationship: It talks about the extent to which the employee believes that getting a good performance appraisal leads to organizational rewards.
- Rewards-personal goals relationship: It is all about the attractiveness or appeal of the potential reward to the individual.

Vroom was of the view that employees consciously decide whether to perform or not at the job. This decision solely depended on the employee's motivation level which in turn depends on three factors of expectancy, valence, and instrumentality.

Porter-Lawler Theory is similar to the Expectancy Theory of motivation in that they agree with the premise that an individual is motivated to complete an action based on what they expect to receive upon completion. This theory further delineates the two types of rewards or benefits that we might expect to get upon reaching a goal. Intrinsic rewards come from within us and include rewards such as self-satisfaction or feeling a sense of accomplishment. Extrinsic rewards include rewards such as a pay raise or bonus for reaching a sales goal

2.3.2.2 Goal Theory (Latham and Locke)

In 1960's, Edwin Locke put forward the Goal-setting theory of motivation. This theory states that goal setting is essentially linked to task performance. It states that specific and challenging goals along with appropriate feedback contribute to higher and better task performance.

In simple words, goals indicate and give direction to an employee about what needs to be done and how much efforts are required to be put in.

Goal theory as later designed by Latham and Locke (1979) states that motivation and performance are higher when individuals set specific goals when goals are difficult but accepted, and when there is feedback on performance. Participation in goal setting is important as a means of getting agreement to the setting of higher goals. Difficult goals must be agreed and their achievement reinforced by guidance and advice

The Needs Goal-Setting Theory puts forth the idea that individuals respond with great motivation when they presented with a goal that appears achievable, has clear parameters, and will garner them positive feedback. The number one thing that motivates us, according to the Needs Goal-Setting Theory, is our own desire to work. The parameters that will cause an individual to want to work are a goal that fits into his value scheme, a goal that is clear and specific, a goal that is challenging but realistic and positive feedback from those around the individual. According to this theory, knowing that we have multiple, particularly defined tasks to complete within a finite amount of time will motivate us to complete the tasks more quickly than if we had one ambiguous, long-term goal.

2.3.2.3 Equity Theory (Adams)

The Equity Theory of motivation is a process theory that explores an individual's motivation to work based on the fairness or sense of equality he detects in the relationship, comparing the amount of effort he puts into any given situation to the benefits he is receiving. If there is any type of inequality perceived, the individual will feel distressed, whether he is giving too much or giving too little, and will act to rectify the inequity. The core of the equity theory is the principle of balance or equity. As per this motivation theory, an individual's motivation

level is correlated to his perception of equity, fairness, and justice practiced by the management. Higher is individual's perception of fairness; greater is the motivation level and vice versa. While evaluating fairness, employee compares the job input (in terms of contribution) to the outcome (in terms of compensation) and also compares the same with that of another peer of equal cadre/category.

As suggested by Adams (1965), there are two forms of equity: distributive equity, which is concerned with the fairness with which people feel they are rewarded in accordance with their contribution and in comparison with others; and procedural equity, or procedural justice, which is concerned with the perceptions employees have about the fairness with which procedures in such areas as performance appraisal, promotion and discipline are being operated. Interpersonal factors are closely linked to feelings about procedural fairness. Five factors that contribute to perceptions of procedural fairness have been identified by Tyler and Bies (1990). These are:

- Adequate considerations of an employee's viewpoint;
- Suppression of personal bias towards the employee
- Applying criteria consistently across employees;
- Providing early feedback to employees concerning the outcome of decisions;
- Providing employees with an adequate explanation of the decision made.

2.4 THEORIES AND THERE IMPLICATIONS

An understanding of motivation is important within reward management and the development of reward strategies for a multitude of reasons. Firstly, it enables organizations to 'humanize' work for employees so that work is inherently more satisfying, the assumption being that organizations have a moral obligation to do work as satisfying and enjoyable as possible. Secondly, an appropriate understanding of motivation allows organizations to make the jobs more satisfying for employees within the company. The underlying assumption is clearly that if employees are happier at work, then they will be more productive. However, these theories have implication which when studied properly will best advice on which one will be more appropriate to use.

2.4.1 Content theory and its implication

Referencing the need component, it is implied that:

- As far as the physiological needs are concerned, the managers should give employees appropriate salaries to purchase the basic necessities of life. Breaks and eating opportunities should be given to employees.
- As far as the safety needs are concerned, the managers should provide the employee's job security, safe and hygienic work environment, and retirement benefits so as to retain them.
- As far as social needs are concerned, the management should encourage teamwork and organize social events
- As far as self-actualization needs are concerned, the managers can give the employees challenging jobs in which the employees' skills and competencies are fully utilized. Moreover, growth opportunities can be given to them so that they can reach the peak
- As far as esteem needs are concerned, the managers can appreciate and reward employees for accomplishing and exceeding their targets. The management can give the deserved employee higher job rank / position in the organization
- The Two-Factor theory implies that the managers must stress upon guaranteeing the adequacy of the hygiene factors to avoid employee dissatisfaction. Also, the managers must make sure that the work is stimulating and rewarding so that the employees are motivated to work and perform harder and better.
- Quite a few organizations use Theory X today. Theory X encourages the use of tight control and supervision. It implies that employees are reluctant to organizational changes. Thus, it does not encourage innovation
- Many organizations are using Theory Y techniques. Theory Y implies that the managers should create and encourage a work environment which provides opportunities to employees to take the initiative and self-direction

2.4.2 Process/Cognitive Theory

Exponents of this component theory based their implications on the pretext that:

- The theory demonstrates that the individuals are concerned both with their own rewards and also with what others get in their comparison. Employees expect a fair and equitable return for their contribution to their jobs.
- The managers can correlate the preferred outcomes to the aimed performance levels.
- The managers must ensure that the employees can achieve the aimed performance levels.
- The deserving employees must be rewarded for their exceptional performance
- The employee's motivation level should be continually assessed through various techniques such as questionnaire, personal interviews, etc.
- Organizations must design interesting, dynamic and challenging jobs.
- The reward system must be fair and just in an organization

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Developing an institution requires a perfect selection of the motivation principle to adopt. Therefore measuring the style adopted by this institution requires us to go through secondary materials written on the said topic as to help us deduce which of the theories will be better used to achieve what is desired by the administrators. I, therefore, used the qualitative approach to measure the methods that I deemed more efficient in this institution. For an institution to achieve its goal, it must bring into memory that employees are seeking for both financial and non-financial reward so as to get them motivated.

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is the opinion of the writers that when money is used as a form of payment or other sorts or remuneration will generate satisfaction as it is an extrinsic type of motivation. We, however, will believe that, though the lack of money will cause dissatisfaction, still having it does not give everlasting satisfaction. There is something in this, especially for people on fixed salaries or rates of pay who do not benefit directly from an incentive scheme. They may feel good when they get an increase; apart from the extra money, it is a highly tangible form of recognition and an effective means of helping people to feel that they are valued. But this feeling of euphoria can rapidly die away especially when salaries do not come at the expected time.

What cannot be assumed is that money motivates everyone in the same way and to the same extent. Thus it is naïve to think that the introduction of a performance-related pay scheme will miraculously transform everyone overnight into well-motivated, high-performing individuals.

Nevertheless, money is a powerful force because it is linked directly or indirectly to the satisfaction of many needs. Money may in itself have no intrinsic meaning, but it acquires significant motivating power because it comes to symbolize so many intangible goals. It acts as a symbol in different ways for different people and for the same person at different times.

But do financial motivations motivate people? The answer is yes, for those people who are strongly motivated by money and whose expectations are that they will receive a financial reward, are high. But less confident employees may not respond to incentives that they do not expect to achieve. It can also be argued that extrinsic rewards may erode intrinsic interest – people who work just for money could find their tasks less pleasurable and may not, therefore, do them so well. What we do know is that a multiplicity of factors is involved in performance improvements and many of those factors are interdependent.

The difficulty of the method of motivation means that basic approaches based on instrumentality theory are questionable to be successful. People are more likely to be motivated if they work in an environment in which they are valued for what they are and what they do. This means paying attention to the basic need for recognition. The administrators should develop reward systems which provide opportunities for both financial and non-financial rewards to identify successes. They should realize that financial rewards systems are not

essentially suitable and the lessons of expectancy, goal and equity theory need to be taken into account in designing and operating them.

4.1 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Having gone through the concept of motivation and its theories, one is obliged to use the content theory for various reasons. The Content theory seeks into those job factors which are essential for the existence of motivation in the workplace. These do not lead to positive satisfaction for long-term. But if these factors are absent or if these factors are non-existent at the workplace, then they lead to dissatisfaction. In other words, the content theory factors are those factors which when adequate/reasonable in a job, pacify the employees and do not make them dissatisfied. The Content theory realizes that:

- **Pay** - The pay or salary structure should be appropriate and reasonable. It must be equal and competitive to those in the same faculty in the same educational level and status.
- **Education Policies and administrative policies** - The education policies should not be too rigid. They should be fair and clear. It should include flexible working hours, dress code, breaks, vacation, etc.
- **Fringe benefits** - The employees should be offered health care plans benefits for the family members, employee help programmes, etc.
- **Status** - The employees' status within the institution should be familiar and retained.
- **Interpersonal relations** - The relationship of the employees with his peers, superiors, and subordinates should be appropriate and acceptable. There should be no conflict or humiliation element present.
- **Recognition** - The employees should be praised and recognized for their accomplishments by the managers.
- **The sense of achievement** - The employees must have a sense of achievement. This depends on the job. There must be a fruit of some sort in the job.
- **Growth and promotional opportunities** - There must be growth and advancement opportunities in an organization to motivate the employees to perform well.
- **Responsibility** - The employees must hold themselves responsible for the work. The managers should give them ownership of the work. They should minimize control but retain accountability.
- **The meaningfulness of the work** - The work itself should be meaningful, interesting and challenging for the employee to perform and to get motivated.

Conclusively, the content theory is more applicable in a conducive work environment for effective output and for workers retention. Though the process theory is also usable as no one theory can be used exclusive, yet I found the content theory with more positive implication than the Process theory.

The administrators should also focus on processes for the design of jobs which take account of the factors affecting the motivation to work, providing for job enrichment in the shape of variety, decision-making responsibility and as much control as possible in carrying out the work. They must also provide facilities and opportunities for learning through such means as personal development planning processes as well as more formal training

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